

FEATURES OF THE STATE OF MIND OF STUDENTS OF MEDICAL AND NON-MEDICAL SPECIALTIES

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Abstract. *Depression is one of the most serious problems in modern health care. Despite the importance of the problem, in most cases, the diagnosis and treatment of depression is not given enough attention, both medical and Social (high risk of suicide, negative impact on social activity, quality of life and a person's ability to adapt). At the same time as depression, anxiety and irritability can occur.*

Keywords: *medical students, mental state, depression, medical diagnostics, medical and social impact.*

Introduction. Mental development in adolescence is largely determined by initial professionalism. Within the framework of this process, the foundation for the student's further achievements is the success of his adaptation to study in a professional educational institution, and therefore it seems relevant to study the process of adapting students to educational conditions, a new lifestyle for them, in particular, to study the features of the mental states of first-year students [1, 4, 7].

The adaptation issues of first-year students have been studied by the following researchers. Ikon understands the process of adaptation through adaptation, the voluntary implementation of the norms and values learned in the context of a given situation [3]. In this case, we are talking about the adaptation of 1st year students college life. Adaptation is the process of adapting the basic parameters of the student's social and personal characteristics to the basic conditions of the student Environment [2, 5].

E. V. Korepanova notes the ever-increasing intensity of mental labor and neuropsychic stress in the first year of Professional Education [5]. In addition to the above, it is also important for rural youth to change their place of residence, which can lead to difficulties in adaptation due to distance from the family, feelings of loneliness and unusual living conditions. This group of students enters more intensive life when entering college than in rural areas, switching to independent active activities. The size of the academic load increases, which makes it difficult to master academic subjects. Adaptation occurs in another team, new relationships are established with classmates [6, 8].

It is assumed that under the influence of a new lifestyle and activity of 1st year students, changes in their mental state occur. N. D. Levitov identified the state of mind as: "...it is an integral characteristic of mental activity for a certain period of time, indicating the specificity of mental processes depending on the objects and phenomena of reflected activity, the previous state and mental characteristics of the individual" [9, 11,14].

As noted, mental states functionally associate mental processes and mental properties. Mental states determine the performance characteristics of the psyche over a certain period of time [10].

Any modern society that takes care of its future development determines the protection of the health of citizens as a priority of full-fledged activities, since health is the most important condition for the active, creative and full-fledged life of a person, a factor in ensuring economic security and progressiveness of State Development. Strengthening the health of the population, significantly reducing the level of socially significant diseases, creating conditions for leading a healthy lifestyle and forming motivation [12-19]. Within the framework of this program, a special place is occupied by the problem of the health of the younger generation, including students, who are not only a representative group of the youth of our country, but also provide a special way for the potential political and socio-economic stability of the state through the training of highly qualified personnel in the specially created conditions [20-26]

Medical students-a specific category of students taught in special conditions: educational load, which is 2 times more than the load of students of non-medical universities; interaction with negatively colored knowledge (suffering, illness, death, etc.); psycho-emotional stress in practical classes "in the hostel", morally saturated communication with patients and their relatives, etc. against this background, they often develop addictive behaviors that manifest themselves in the form of smoking, alcohol, psychoactive substances, etc [27-31].

The main reasons for the development of these situations are a constant increase in the rhythm of modern human life, an increase in the number of stressful and stressful situations. It is no secret that one of the most stressed and constantly stressed categories of the population is students. But there are groups among students that have a more and less negative impact. This is primarily due to the specialties under study, which require different levels of responsibility, time and determination [32-36]. And one of the most difficult specialties is a doctor. There are many obstacles on the way to obtaining a diploma from a medical student, which negatively affects the state of mind.

The purpose of our study was to compare the mental state of students of medical and non-medical specialties.

The purpose of the study is to assess the mental state of students of Samarkand State Medical University and Samarkand State Pedagogical University.

Materials and methods. The study included 90 students of the 4th course: 30 students of the Faculty of treatment of Samarkand State Medical University and 30 students of Samarkand State Pedagogical University. The median age of students was 21 years.

Students are not gender-based. The survey was conducted in the form of a survey. The questionnaire consisted of 3 parts: Part 1 included academic indicators, general questions about the attitude to study and its mental state; Part 2 and Part 3 used the anxiety and depression scale (HADS) at the hospital.

Typically, the measurement results range from 0 to 7 points, in the presence of subclinically specific anxiety/depression - 8-10 points, in the presence of clinically specific anxiety / depression - 11 points and above. For ease of comparison, all results were transferred to percentages.

Results and their discussion. 6,6% of students have identified subclinically specific anxiety, and as many students have subclinically specific depression. The remaining students did not deviate from the norm. At the same time, 69,3% of students study at "4" and "5", and 86,8%

manage to pursue other hobbies. 83,5% of all students of this faculty believe that the load on the educational institution is not more than on others. And to the question: "Do you think that your mental state has deteriorated while studying at the University?" 63,7% of students responded "No". 9,9% of students have identified subclinically specific anxiety and 3,3% have clinically specific anxiety. 29,7% have subclinically distinct depression and 3,3% have clinically distinct depression. At the same time, 60,4% of students study at "4" and "5", and 93,4% manage to engage in other hobbies. 53.8% of students believe that the loads in an educational institution are not higher than others. And 57,1% of students reported a deterioration in mental state during their studies.

Among treatment faculty students, 13,2% identified subclinically defined anxiety, while 3,3% identified clinically defined anxiety. 39,6% have subclinically distinct depression and 9,9% have clinically distinct depression. At the same time, only 47,2% of students study at "4" and "5", and only 59,4% manage to engage in other hobbies. Almost all students, 96,7%, believe that their institutions have a higher burden than others. And 70,3% of students recorded a deterioration in mental state during their studies.

Conclusion. According to the results of a study on the anxiety and depression scale (HADS), academic indicators, load assessment and personal assessment of the mental state of students, the worst indicators among students of the Faculty of treatment, more favorable indicators for students of the Faculty of pedagogy and the most favorable indicators for the rest were identified – students. Thus, it can be said that the mental state of medical specialty students is worse than that of non-medical specialty students.

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